

Job Satisfaction and Employee Work Attitude (A Case Study of Employees Working In Commercial Banks In District Nausharo-Feroze-2015)

Author's Details: ⁽¹⁾Dr: Muneer Ahmed Shah-⁽²⁾Faheem -ul-Hussain Dehraj⁽³⁾Bilawal Ali Dayo ⁽¹⁾Associate Professor, Department of Business Administration, Shah Abdul Latif University Khairpur, Sindh, Pakistan
⁽²⁾⁽³⁾M.PHIL/MS Scholar-Department of Business Administration, Shah Abdul Latif University Khairpur, Sindh, Pakistan

Abstract:

Looking at the need and importance of employee's job satisfaction for organizational success, this research was made by using workplace environment, salary, benefits and team effectiveness/work group as an independent variables for the job satisfaction, questionnaires were developed for collection of primary data from the employees of both working in public and private commercial banks at District Nausharo-feroze, SPSS 18 was used for measuring the role of discussed above variables and concluded that salary, benefits and team effectiveness/work group positively and significantly linked with job satisfaction, while the relationship between workplace environment is adversely seen to job satisfaction, however gap is seen so large to be fulfilled by other researchers to bring light on same issue.

Key words: Work place environment, Salary & Benefits, Team effectiveness/work group, Job satisfaction.

Introduction:

This research is carried out to discover the co-relationship among job satisfaction and some other factors as compensation, work environment, team effectiveness except depend on one factor. The research contains both intrinsic elements "like recognition and accomplishments", where as other extrinsic element concerned with working situations, safety and compensation for the satisfaction evaluation of employees. Intrinsic elements are useful in assessing logic of accomplishments and hazard taking capacities and job challenges faced to employees, where as extrinsic elements concerned to behavior and attitude to career development, remuneration, bonus and possible rise in income.

This does sense, escalating efficiency would execute essential role in rising progress of the organization, different elements influence the organizational effectiveness but employees satisfaction is major one of these. Efficient organizations must have environment that motivates the employee's satisfaction (Bhatti & Qureshi, 2007).

Different organizations are joined by people in their longer part of lives. The organizations are potential societal tool in managing affiliation among the individuals. Organizations acts as a constitution where together people come to avail their goals and behaviors are administrated according to particular principles (Applewhite, 1965).

The organizations ever are goal oriented and a societal maintained system of human action that concentrates the focus on the social method occupied in the origins and perservance of organization. When someone desires to attain his goals these needs much strength than one's has, he should interact with others, this makes sense organization fulfill the one's need through interactive and mutually work environment (Aldrich, 1999).

The aim of this research is to assess the satisfaction level of employees working in public and private commercial banks in District nausharoferoze and Gambat, its' impact on performance of employees working environment. The results of this research will be helpful to address the complex problems, affecting working conditions and the internal and external customer's expectations, and will provide the meaningful HR suggestions to practice.

Review of literature: 1

1.1 work place environment

Employees become so devoted and efficient (Hunter & Tietyen, 1997) , when they are pleased, where as customer satisfaction and organization output affected by these employee satisfaction.

The intricacy of environmental modification firms to quest more effective equipped progressive process. This does sense, escalating efficiency would execute essential role in rising progress of the organization, different elements influence the organizational effectiveness but employees satisfaction is major one of these. Efficient organizations must have environment that motivates the employee’s satisfaction (Bhatti & Qureshi, 2007).

Work place of workers and work regulation are concerned to working condition. Organization role and job related training (Ceylan, 1998), capacities exploitation, healthy, safe, neat and disciplined working environment creates employee's satisfaction.

(Ozdevecioglu, 2000) concluded that employee’s satisfaction is one of key fundamental of organizational performance behavior, this mean that well satisfied personnel would work more enthusiastically and ultimately leads to the efficiency of the organization.

1.2 Salary and Benifits

Some other factors have influences on employee job satisfaction such as bonus plan, incentive benefits, competitive salary and freedom like holidays, sick leave because pleased employees are useful, these rewards enhance the effectiveness of workers and self assurance, it is vital that firms observe the workers attitude, therefore survey attitude must be executed in informing top executive from productive feedback that how workers realize their job conditions. (Beer, Spector, Lawrence, Mills, & Walton, 1984).

For employee’s satisfaction, reputation and acceptance are considered as essential elements (Maurer, 2001), whereas organization attainment affiliated with employee contentment by honor and esteem.

Several researchers argued that attitude influences behavior, one’s attitude associated with wok satisfaction, job participation, organizational steadfastness, where as salary, job place, technology and environmental transformation each of these major elements affects employee’s behavior of all sort of organization (Igalens & Roussel, 1999).

Few factors concerned to job satisfaction such as work place environment, location, income and timing of work (Bodur, 2002), several theories have been emerged to job satisfaction among these one of essential theory is Maslow’s need theory support to”human hierarchical needs”, Maslow’s theory depends on basic and external factors for instance, recognition, achievement, compensation, interpersonal relation, operational environment as well management.

Some usual recognized factors being considered for job satisfaction like career advancement opportunities, remuneration satisfaction, health plan, team work, direction and work himself (Smith, Kendall, & Hulin, 1969).

These aspects of job usually result for considerable reasons of a changing in job satisfaction (Kinicki, McKee-Reyan, Schriesheim, & Carson, 2002).

Lincoln & Kallerberg (1990) concluded that rewad proposed through organization have influence to emplyee’s attitude of their jobs the organization for they work. According two factor theory of Herzberg and Mausner’s the rewards in shape of intrinsic or extrinsic affecting the degree of job satisfaction (Hong, While, & Barriball, 2005).

1.3 Team effectiveness/Work Group

Daulatram (2003) reported that overall quality of work to meet the external and internal expectations of customers and other stake holders, employees job co-operation is essential, where workers and executives

accept group work, effective team work accelerate employees work effectiveness and creating jobs rotation in organization, where workers jobs in similar context.

Valnampy(2008) reported in his research about job satisfaction and human resources performance, based on better performance and the collaborative work environment rises the degree of superior attainment of organization goal.

In the era of today’s understanding the importance of human resource, mostly by focusing the working practices considered essential to enhance the company performance through rising individual efficiency with staffing, reward system, individual participation, training, job advancement (Boselie, 2002) .

Research model: 2

Hypothesis: 3

H1: Work place environment positively related with job satisfaction (JS).

H2: Salary and Benefits positively related with job satisfaction (JS).

H3: Team effectiveness and work group positively related with job satisfaction (JS).

Methodology: 4

Primary data: Primary source of information was used to collect the data through developing a questionnaire in English language comprises of three variable factors by using five point measuring scale (strongly agree, agree, disagree, strongly disagree, don’t know).

Secondary data: Review of literature was used that defending our research work with perspective to different research papers of many authors were reviewed.

Sampling: Data was collected randomly from 196 employees working in both public and private commercial banks at district Nausharo-feroze.

Statistically method: spss18 software was used to assess the reliability of the instrument by crombachs alpha, followed through analysis; following four variables were used for confirmatory analysis.

1: work place environment

2: Salary and Benefits

3: Team effectiveness and work group

4: Job satisfaction

Diagnostic test: 5 $JS = \alpha + WPE1 \beta_1 + S \& B2 \beta_2 + TE/ WG3 \beta_3 + \mu$

JS= Job satisfaction (dependent variable)

WPE = work place environment (independent variable)

S & BS = Salary & Benefits (independent variable)

TE/WG= Team effectiveness/ Work group (independent variable).

Results & Discussions: 6

Regression analysis:

$JS = \alpha + WPE1 \beta_1 + S \& B2 \beta_2 + TE/ WG3 \beta_3 + \mu$

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.678a	.459	.451	.74118530

a. Predictors: (Constant), Work group, workplace environment, salary and benefits

Over all fitness of model is identified by the measure of Adjusted R Square, representing the value of Adjusted R Square is .451, which indicate that 45% of fit this model, which suggest that each of these three independent variables like work place environment, salary and benefits and work group is contributing just 45% job satisfaction, however rest of 55% is an error term.

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	89.974	3	29.991	54.594	.000 ^a
	Residual	106.026	193	.549		
	Total	196.000	196			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Work group, work place environment, salary and benefits

b. Dependent Variable: Job satisfaction

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-2.808E-16	.053		.000	1.000
	Workplace environment	-.035	.053	-.035	-.659	.511
	Salary and benefits	.237	.065	.237	3.667	.000
	Work group	.510	.065	.510	7.904	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Job satisfaction

As per results shown in the above presented table that there is inverse relationship between organizational climate and job satisfaction, however strength of both these is not stable, where as Salary and benefits, work group is positively related with job satisfaction and the strength of these both variables is not so much strong but significant.

Conclusion: 7

For organizational success value to employees is utmost demanded to get their job satisfaction, which are focusing on organizational climate, total compensation, work group and team effectiveness, it is not necessary that satisfaction can prevail only focusing on organizational climate but to be focused on including total compensation , work group and team effectiveness as well.

Limitations & recommendations: 8

This research is delimited to the premises of District Nausharo-feroze, results may change time to time as per policies made by banking industry to manage its employees. This research contributes just 45% comprised of four variables work place environment, salary and benefits, team effectiveness/work group, remaining 55% is needed yet to be researched by the researchers.

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